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MAX phases triggered in-situ TiC and γ' - $\text{Ni}_3(\text{Al},\text{Ti})$ synergistically reinforced nickel matrix composite

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Contents

1

Reaction mechanism in the $\text{Ti}_2\text{AlC-Ni}$ system

2

Interfacial analysis on $\text{TiC-}\gamma$ and γ'/γ

3

Mechanical properties of $\text{TiC-}\gamma'/\text{Ni}$

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01

Reaction mechanism in the $\text{Ti}_2\text{AlC-Ni}$ system

1. Gibbs Free Energy of Products

The sequence of formations:
 $Ni_3(Al,Ti) > TiC > NiAl > NiTi$

2. TG-DTA (30 Ti_2AlC/Ni)

900 °C Exothermic peak: indicating Ti_2AlC begins to decompose
 1365 °C endothermic peak: indicating that there was liquid phase formation, and the dissolution of al-ti reduced the melting point of Ni.

3. Ni-Ti-Al Ternary Diagram (900 °C)

900 °C, Al-Ti solubility in Ni:
 ~11 at. %

- A-10 Ti_2AlC/Ni
- B-20 Ti_2AlC/Ni
- C-30 Ti_2AlC/Ni
- D-40 Ti_2AlC/Ni

4. Phase evolution in matrix

Reaction:

Topotactic Transformation:

Coherent $L1_2$:
 $Ni_3(Al,Ti)$

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02

Interfacial analysis on TiC- γ and γ'/γ

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Interfacial analysis on TiC- γ and γ' / γ

TiC与 γ -Ni:
Simi-coherent:
 $(020)\text{TiC} // (111)\text{Ni}$
 $[001]\text{TiC} // [011]\text{Ni}$

γ -Ni与 γ' -Ni₃(Al,Ti):
coherent:
 $\{100\}_{\gamma'} // \{100\}_{\gamma}$
 $\langle 010 \rangle_{\gamma'} // \langle 010 \rangle_{\gamma}$

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TiC-Ni₃(Al,Ti)/Ni composite after thermal treatment

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03

Mechanical properties of TiC- γ' /Ni

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High-temperature mechanical properties

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Thanks for your attention!

